

HUMAN ECOLOGY AND FACTORS AFFECTING THE EXTERNAL ENVIRONMENT ON THE HUMAN BODY

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Abstract. *Based on the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-76 "Ecology and Environment" which dated December 30, 2021, so it was designated as the International Day of Environmental Protection on 5 June. As part of the celebration of this day, the UN informs the international community about environmental problems that are urgent worldwide and calls on the peoples of the world to solve these problems. "Ecology and Environment" states that awareness and conscious engagement of each individual is one of the most important issues in strengthening the ecological situation, and studies the basis of human health. In the article, human ecology or anthropoecology is the central part of social society, its socio-natural and natural-scientific basis. Human ecology summarizes relevant views of demography, medicine, morphology, anthropology, and genetics.*

Keywords: *component, morphology, anthropology, anthropodemoecosystem, biosphere, noosphere, anthropoecosystem, evolution, biogeocenosis, coevolution, UN, UNESCO, UNEP, WHO.*

Introduction. Today, with the rapid development of science and technology, the attitude of man to the environment changes, and he tries to get more natural resources today than yesterday, tomorrow than today. As this process intensified, the ecological balance, which had been stable for thousands of years, was disturbed, the relationship between man and nature became complicated, and nature came to the brink of disaster. Of course, it is necessary to use natural resources, but to use them everywhere according to the need, in moderation, to consistently enrich nature, especially to maintain the natural relationship between its components (organizers) of plants and animals. necessary.

When we say human ecology, we understand the changes that occur in the human body due to the influence of various factors in the external environment. Human ecology is a very diverse science, which includes all factors of the external environment, air temperature, light, humidity, radiation, noise, weightlessness, as well as various natural disasters, earthquakes, hurricanes, droughts, floods, fires. the interaction of organisms and living organisms is understood. The effect of all these factors does not depend on the will of a person. In addition to these, the toxic wastes from the enterprises, irrigation facilities, vehicles, and chemical substances widely used in agriculture pollute the air, water, land, and the quality of food products, causing great harm to human health.

These sciences are combined in one piece on the basis of the fact that the object of research is the same. That object is a person, he is a rare creature belonging to two worlds, natural and

social. In this case, it should be noted that the main object of attention in the study of man in connection with the problem of "man - natural environment" is not man in general and even his ecology, but the part of human ecology that manifests itself through the connection with nature.

Human ecology is a complex interdisciplinary scientific direction. He studies the laws of interaction of human populations with the environment, the growth of the population under the influence of this interaction, the problems of goal-oriented management, the problems of maintaining and developing the health of the population. It is clear that in human ecology, in its main directions, the socio-targeted basis prevails, because the study of the direct interaction of man with nature through society is the objective content of this subject.

From this point of view, human ecology is a branch of social ecology that studies the laws of interaction between humans and the natural and social environment that surrounds them, or a scientific direction about socio-biological relations within the anthropodemoecosystem.

Taking into account the morpho-physiological characteristics of the person, in the process of non-spheric changes, it is an important task of human ecology to reveal the laws of exploitation of the regions of the Earth, regions of the biosphere for production - economic, economic purposes, in the course of such exploitation, to study the natural laws of the preservation and development of human health. . According to V. I. Vernadsky's theory of the noosphere, human ecology occupies a special place in modern natural science. Vernadsky talks about the ever-increasing anthropogenic burden on nature, about humanity as a factor that changes nature, about the comparison of influencing nature with its possibilities, that is, about what we now call the coevolution of man and the biosphere. But at the same time, in all his comments, the idea that man is responsible for the perspective of the biosphere, and the idea of organizing society in such a way as to allow rational direction of the evolution of the biosphere, is a red thread.

Human ecology, as an expression of the natural and social environment surrounding people, and the relationship of people to it and to each other, was introduced into the scientific literature for the first time by the American sociologists R. Park and U. Burgess. A little later, the English scientist U. Byus explains that the task of "Human ecology" is to connect the social relations of people with biological population processes and tries to solve it based on the traditional concepts of biological ecology. The concentration of industry and people in large cities, industrialization, air and water pollution, and the use of drugs have made it necessary to study pathology (exit in normal cases). They brought serious changes to the process of natural evolution, biogeocenoses, and changed the closed ecological system.

The goal of studying human ecology is to create an optimal (comfortable) environment for human life. Environmental disasters that have occurred, people of our planet to look for measures to prevent disasters is pushing. Such a situation requires a new approach to socio-economic political, moral, ecological, cultural and historical issues. That is, it makes people to think in a new way, the place and role of man in nature. Natural disasters have happened in nature before. However, many environmental disasters that have occurred in the present era were caused by human activity, which is a part of nature.

Today, people living on our planet face the task of solving the problems of the relationship between human society and external nature. With the increase in the number of people on our planet, the needs of people and the impact on mother nature are increasing. If in 1850 there were 1 billion people, in 1930 it reached 2 billion, and now it has exceeded five billion. Regardless of the relationship of a person with the environment, the issue of the exchange of generations, the

process of population growth in a stable state is always important. The continuity of life is provided by the interaction of two opposing currents. These are the streams of birth and death. In order for society and humanity to exist, there must be a certain harmony between these two streams. If the birth rate is less than the death rate for a long period of time, humanity will suffer. If this relationship is reversed, the rapid increase of the population creates a strain on the ecological and socio-economic capabilities of the society. Therefore, keeping these two currents in a harmonious state is one of the most important tasks of the society, and a lot of social effort is spent to solve it.

Humanity began life in a state of initial ecological balance inherited from the past. But during the recovery period, the society managed to get out of strict control of natural ecological systems, biological and ecological factors due to collective work. In particular, both the process of reproduction and the use of weapons, humans or their close ancestors learned to take more from nature than other creatures in nature. At that time, a "social shield" was created to protect against the adverse effects of the human natural environment.

The industry created by man to improve his life and vehicles have affected the climate of our planet, thinning of the ozone layer, depletion of forests, water pollution, soil erosion, and desertification in many places. In addition, man-made radioactive radiation, excessive use of chemicals led to the proliferation of disease-causing viruses and microorganisms, and the emergence of new types of diseases.

In almost all countries of the world, all privileges are first given to their own people. For example, it includes accommodation, employment, setting higher wages for their own people than foreigners, or providing goods, etc. For many years, it has been the opposite for us. All the above-mentioned natural factors, disasters, and social injustices affect the human body as an extreme factor, causing it to be in a state of stress (hard mental shock). Stressed people suffer from insomnia, fatigue, anger, headaches, and high blood pressure.

Anthropoecosystem is a research object of human ecology. Different groups of human populations or ethnos living together in a dialectical relationship with each other and the surrounding natural and social environment are called anthropoecological system or anthropoecotism. This science studies the interaction of people and nature, man and the biosphere in close connection with specific social, economic and political conditions of life.

Today, it has already become clear that human health is a consequence of the complex history of society and its current development. Therefore, none of the natural sanitary-hygiene measures, no matter how scientifically based and technically advanced they are, cannot by themselves maintain, develop, and protect the health of the members of the society. Scientific organization of the social production economy structure of the whole society, creation of work and rest conditions, conditions of spiritual and physical training, development of lifestyle culture - all these are a condition and guarantee of health protection and strengthening. These problems can be solved only when the interaction of the society with natural conditions is directed to the improvement of this effect. It covers all geographical regions, all processes in animate and inanimate nature, all areas of our planet. Here it is not just about protecting nature, but about preserving and developing nature in order to create favorable social and ecological conditions for the further improvement of harmony between man and nature. Nature protection is one of the most important means to achieve the highest goal - a comprehensively developed human and human society. Human ecology is not subject to only biological laws, and it cannot be understood without interaction of these laws with social laws. This is explained by many reasons. The first reason is

that T.N. Fedoseev states that - modern science and technology revolution, among other things, leads to the fact that man himself makes various and always unpredictable changes in human ecology, which in turn these changes have a no less significant impact. As a result, acute and largely unsolved problems of human adaptation to such changes appear.

Interactions between man, society and nature are not built on the basis of biological and ecological principles, but on the principles of social work that changes them. Man's relationship to nature and nature's relationship to man are realized through social production forces, production relations and specific labor processes in which man participates.

Modern human ecology covers and studies local, regional and global problems of the interaction of man, society and nature from the point of view of their interaction with living nature and man. Nature protection is one of the most important means of achieving the highest goal - a comprehensively developed human and human society. Life is a supreme gift that is given to everyone once. A human life is a moment in history. So, he should live happily and beautifully in his short life. Man is an inseparable part of nature. A person's normal life depends on the ecological health of the nature that surrounds him. That is why we need to improve human life and make nature ecologically healthy. The health and spiritual maturity of each person is very necessary not only for him, but also for the future development of our society.

At the end of the 20th century, the influence of humanity on the processes in the biosphere reached its highest stage. Local, regional and universal ecological crisis situations are observed before the eyes of the present generation. The correct assessment of the state of the environment and the timely implementation of necessary measures are directly related to the level of development of environmental knowledge. Environmental education of the growing young generation should be started from the family and continued in kindergarten, school, colleges and universities. Since ecology is diverse, it should be inculcated in the minds of young people through all sciences. It is very important to organize excursions and hikes in the heart of nature in providing ecological education to young people.

Environmental education and training is the focus of the UN, UNESCO, UNEP, and WHO. (UNESCO is an independent organization of the United Nations that deals with science and culture. Its headquarters is located in Paris. The United Nations itself is located in New York City, which includes 190 countries in the world.) Environmental education and training various activities are being held at the level of the world and individual countries for development. Every specialist in the field should be ecologically literate and should not harm the nature in his activities, should contribute to the development of ecological education. Therefore, teaching children to take care of plants and animals, raising them in the spirit of love for nature is not just a pastime, it is an urgent issue of national importance.

Our future will be bright only when we are able to raise healthy, moral, hardworking, pure and knowledgeable young people. Everyone should contribute to the sacred work of changing the nature of our mother planet without harming it, using its natural resources wisely, and preserving the living environment.

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